

Proposed a Design Company Performance Management System by Using Balanced Scorecard in a Nickel Mining Company (Case: PT Gema Kreasi Perdana)

Sara Nadira Marpaung¹, Dermawan Wibisono², Muhammad Hanafi³

¹²³School of Business Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Indonesia is one of the countries that has the largest nickel reserves in the world. In the Asian region, Indonesia's nickel laterite reserves are in the third position. Indonesia's nickel reserves are around 800 thousand tons or about 30% of the world's total nickel production, so that Indonesia has the potential to enjoy the demand for this stainless metal [7]. One of the companies that carry out nickel mining in Southeast Sulawesi Province is PT Gema Kreasi Perdana (GKP). As a newly established company, a variety of strategies are implemented to survive and maintain its corporate existence in the mining industry. The company needs a method for measuring performance in order to monitor and analyze company performance. Implementing a Performance Management System is one way that can be used (PMS). Balanced Scorecard (BSC) is the employed PMS in this investigation. BSC is a method for measuring the performance of a firm by bridging the gap between strategy and execution. Based on a literature review, focus group discussions (FGD), and interviews with expert practitioners in their respective fields, objective strategies are determined for each perspective. The aims and initiatives for key performance indicators (KPIs) are determined based on benchmarking with other businesses and company interviews. Data analysis and weighting from each perspective will be carried out using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. In addition to using goal strategies, the researchers cascaded the process from the Business Unit Level to the Individual Level and limited in the HRGA (Human Resource and General Affair) and Strategic Affair Division of PT Gema Kreasi Perdana. The cascading process is believed important to ensure that the company's vision, mission, and strategy are communicated clearly to all employees. The cascading process is regarded important to ensure that the company's vision, goal, and strategy are communicated clearly to each employee. This cascading produced multiple objective strategies and KPIs for HRGA and Strategic Affair Division of PT GKP. As suggestions for future research, it would be preferable for the research to cascade to all levels within each division in the company.

KEYWORDS: Balanced Scorecard (BSC), Nickel, Mining, Performance Management System (PMS), Strategy

1. INTRODUCTION

The global nickel market has been expanding quickly in recent years. The market is anticipated to increase at a CAGR of 7.3% from 2021 to 2028, from \$36.27 billion to \$59.14 billion. In 2020, the worldwide nickel market was worth 33.31 billion dollars. The market is predicted to increase at a CAGR of 7.3% between 2021 and 2028, from USD 36.27 billion in 2021 to USD 59.14 billion in 2028. The worldwide effect of COVID-19 has been unprecedented and catastrophic, and the pandemic has had a severe influence on nickel demand in all areas. Based on our data, the worldwide market grew by 1.2% in 2020, which was more than the average annual increase from 2017 to 2019. This market's demand and growth are responsible for the abrupt increase in CAGR, which will revert to pre-pandemic levels once the pandemic is ended [4]. Several countries, notably Indonesia, have the highest nickel reserves on the planet. Indonesia has nickel deposits of 21 million tons (37.04 percent of the world's nickel reserves) with an estimated reserve life of 27 years [1]. Currently, nearly 800 thousand tons, or 30 percent of the world's total nickel production, are contained in Indonesia's nickel resources [7], allowing the nation to profit from the demand for this stainless metal. According to the Indonesian Nickel Investment Opportunity report published by the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Indonesia's nickel deposits are dispersed among several areas, with the largest nickel resource (38%) situated in the Sulawesi region, particularly in Southeast Sulawesi. This abundance of natural resources makes Sulawesi the greatest nickel hub in Indonesia. In 2020, about 84% of the 323 permits of mining and production operation licenses and nickel smelters that had been functioning in Indonesia, located in Sulawesi [5]. PT Gema Kreasi Perdana is one of the companies that is involved in the mining of nickel in Sulawesi.

Administratively, PT GKP's mining activities are situated on Wawonii Island, specifically in the Konawe Islands of Southeast Wawonii district, Southeast Sulawesi Province. As a newly founded mining company since 2017, a range of strategies are used to ensure its survival and continued existence in the face of intense competition. As part of the ongoing execution of one of its strategies, PT GKP had swiftly established new departments and increased its workforce. However, the process presents difficulties for the corporate level to track the performance across the company, thus making managerial decision-making very challenging. The organization is also struggling to maintain the desired level of employee performance and to retain personnel who are essential for carrying out duties that are fundamental to the primary business process as well as supporting responsibilities. Therefore, the performance management system method is extremely necessary and significant as a combined tool to convey goals and successes and as a crucial instruction to assess the effectiveness of the organization (Wibisono, 2012) [3].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Balanced Scorecard

According to Kaplan and Norton (1996), the Balanced Scorecard is a technique for measuring CEO performance that necessitates a comprehensive assessment with four perspectives: a financial perspective, a customer perspective, an internal company perspective, and a growth and learning perspective. The Balanced Scorecard is defined by Anthony, Banker, Kaplan, and Young (1997) as "a measuring and management system that evaluates a business unit's performance from four perspectives: financial, customer, internal business process, and learning and growth." The Balanced Scorecard or BSC is a strategic management system (Strategic Responsibility Based Accounting System) that translates a company's mission and strategy into operational objectives and performance measures. The Balanced Scorecard is a scorecard that is used to plan the score that an individual wants to attain in the future and to record the actual performance score that an individual has earned (Munawir 2002: 437). The Balanced Scorecard perspective is as follows:

1. Financial Perspective

The balanced scorecard employs conventional financial performance measures, such as net profit and return on investment (return on investment). These indications cannot stand alone without additional help. In accordance with the BSC principle, there must be a balance between financial and non-financial perspectives.

2. Customer Perspective

In this view, the first step for a corporation is to establish which client market segments it wants to target.

3. Internal Business Process

The internal business process perspective represents the company's major procedures that can be enhanced to enhance the company's value offering and attract and retain consumers.

4. Learning and Development

The learning and growth perspective displays the organization's capacity to develop the following three types of resources or capital:

- a. Human Capital
- b. Organizational Capital
- c. Information Capital

Balanced Scorecard clearly identifies the value drivers for greater long-term financial and competitive success while maintaining, the financial perspective, an interest in short-term performance. A company's main purpose is for making money, especially a profit oriented company. Thus, financial measures are critical in the Balanced Scorecard. Financial objectives represent the long-term goal of the organization: expanding and strengthening PT Gema Kreasi Perdana's business portfolio. The drivers in the financial perspective will be customized to the industry, the competitive environment, and the strategy of the business unit. Kaplan and Norton suggested a classification scheme where business can choose financial objectives from themes relating to revenue growth, create shareholders value, and improve financial strength. All objectives and measures in the other scorecard perspectives should be linked to achieving one or more objectives in the financial perspective. Customers are crucial for PT Gema Kreasi Perdana. As explained in PT Gema Kreasi Perdana's mission, one of which is that PT Gema Kreasi Perdana has a mission to provide added value to customers through strategic and long-term partnerships. In addition to building strategic partnerships, what needs to be emphasized

is to build excellent service quality. Building excellent service quality will provide operational excellence. Apart from operational excellence, there is product leadership as well as customer intimacy. These three perspectives will lead to the customer value proposition. In the internal business perspective, the company identifies the key process where the company must excel in order to continue adding value for customers and ultimately for shareholders. The task here is to identify the internal processes to achieve efficient operation and develop objectives and measures which can track the progress and achievement of the goal aforementioned. d skill and capabilities, it does not mean anything. The objectives and measures in this perspective are the enablers of the other perspectives in the Balanced Scorecard. When the team has identified objectives and measures for customers and internal perspectives, the team might discover some gaps between the current organizational infrastructure of employee skills (human capital), information systems (informational capital), and the environment required to maintain success (organizational capital). The objectives and measures in this perspective will help the company close the gaps and ensure sustainable performance for the future. Strategies for superior performance will generally require significant investments in people, systems, and processes that build organizational capabilities. Cascade is a strategy target derivative in a firm. Cascading, according to Hikmat (2016), is the process of creating a Balanced Scorecard at every level of the organization or company as a means of disseminating strategic goals and initiatives from the highest level of the organization or company to the lowest level of the organization or company [6]. Using a balanced scorecard in a cascading manner entails translating the Corporate Scorecard (Tier 1) down to first business units or Divisions (Tier 2), and then teams or individuals (Tier 3)[2]. Consistent concentration at all organizational levels should be the ultimate outcome. Through strategy, including the strategy map, performance measurements and targets, and activities, the organization alignment should be readily apparent. Through objective and performance measure ownership, scorecards should be used to increase accountability, and desired employee behaviours should be encouraged with praise and awards. A cascading strategy concentrates all organizational efforts on strategy and establishes a link between daily operations and strategic goals. The objectives and performance measures change as the management system cascades down through the company, becoming more operational and tactical. As ownership is established at each level, accountability follows the objectives and metrics. Throughout the business, a focus on results and the tactics required to create success is communicated. For an organization to become strategy focused, this alignment phase is essential.

2.2 Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), which was invented by Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s, is a method for addressing multi-criteria complicated issues. AHP allows decision makers to model in a hierarchical framework by illustrating the relationship between complicated problems, their primary objectives, criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives. The most significant component of AHP is the decision maker's ability to incorporate objective or subjective considerations. In other words, AHP is a strategy that combines an individual's knowledge, experience, thoughts, and premonitions in a logical manner. AHP has a broad scope of application and is utilized efficiently for all types of decision issues. AHP is founded on the following four principles (Saaty, 1994):

1. Arrangement of Hierarchies
The aspects of the problem to be solved, namely criteria and alternatives, are separated and placed hierarchically.
2. Assessment of Criteria and Option
Criteria and alternatives are evaluated using a subjective comparison. The optimal scale for expressing ideas on a variety of subjects is a 1 to 9 range.
3. Prioritization
For each criterion and option, pairwise comparisons must be conducted.
4. Logical Consistency
All elements are organized rationally and consistently ranked according to a logical criterion.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research used a qualitative method and the tool used in this qualitative method is an interview. Descriptive qualitative research was employed to complete this research. Qualitative descriptive research describes or depicts the object of study based on evident facts or as it is (Nawawi and Martini, 1996: 73). By using qualitative descriptive methods, it is intended that the researcher will be able to transmit information through presentations and the provision of data necessary to conduct a Balanced Scorecard Analysis and draw conclusions based on the results of the analysis. In this instance, PT Gema Kreasi Perdana is the study subject, and the

adoption of the Balanced Scorecard in the HRGA (Human Resource and Strategic Affair) and Strategic Affair Division at PT Gema Kreasi Perdana is the research object. An interview is a meeting conducted by two people to exchange information or an idea by way of question and answer, so that it can be used as a conclusion or meaning in the topic (Sugiyono, 2015) [8]. Interviews were conducted with HRGA and Strategic Affair General Manager, HR Support and General Affair Manager, Recruitment Superintendent, Technical Affair Superintendent, and Strategic Communication Superintendent. This strategy enables researchers to gain a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the company's business difficulties from the interviewee's perspective. This study collected primary data through organized and unstructured interviews with several managers and superintendents. The interview approach for the structured interview was the in-depth interview, which was undertaken with the goal of acquiring information from respondents about the subject under study that could not be revealed using questionnaire procedures. This research involves interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) with the HRGA and Strategic Affair General Manager, the HR Support and General Affair Manager, the Recruitment Superintendent, the Technical Affair Superintendent, and the Strategic Communication Superintendent. To acquire secondary data, it was necessary to analyze data such as the company's historical data, relevant research, and journals in addition to conducting interviews.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Vision, Mission, and Value

Vision: "Optimizing the value of our resources to make the best contribution to shareholders, stakeholders and the country."

Mission: "Sustainable excellence through continuous improvement of people and process."

Value:

- a. Humility
Humble and willing to listen to others to create a caring culture.
- b. Achievement Oriented
Achieving the best results continuously based on standard processes in the company.
- c. Respect for Every Individual
Demonstrate interaction with others with politeness according to eastern customs and tolerance and empathy for fellow employees regardless of position/position.
- d. Integrity
Uncompromising in terms of conflicting core values in the company, showing a sincere attitude at work, and being responsible for one's own mistakes.
- e. Teamwork
Oriented to group success and have an abundance mentality (caring, helpful, and sincere).
- f. Accountability
Demonstrate significant effort when facing obstacles in implementing company policies.

4.2 Strategic Plan

With the recovery of the global and national economies, the surge in nickel demand, resulting in an increase in nickel prices, gives the company's business confidence. The fast development dynamic needs the Company to adopt more adaptive strategies and work more creatively and effectively in capturing opportunities and dealing with diverse difficulties in order to maintain a sustainable company. A range of strategies are used to ensure its survival and continued existence in the face of intense competition. As part of the ongoing execution of one of its strategies, PT Gema Kreasi Perdana had swiftly established new departments and increased its workforce. However, the process presents difficulties for the corporate level to track the performance across the company, thus making managerial decision-making very challenging. The organization is also struggling to maintain the desired level of employee performance and to retain personnel who are essential for carrying out duties that are fundamental to the primary business process as well as supporting responsibilities. The business strategy that was formulated below is inseparable from the strategic framework defined by the Company for accomplishing its vision and mission, which comprises of several aspects, namely:

- a. Cost Optimization
Business-focused, continuous discipline to drive spending and cost reduction, while maximizing business value. Maintaining cost efficiency in order to provide a competitive rate and profitability, and employing careful capital management that optimizes resources in order to get the best results.
- b. Operational Excellence
Optimizing all available resources, including all equipment, people, materials, and processes, in order to create results that surpass expectations by providing the best quality. Able to identify and eliminate waste through continuous improvement by flowing product at customer request.
- c. Relationships with the Community
Engaging the surrounding community through establishing long-lasting relationships that foster an environment of support. Positions businesses as civically and ethically responsible into the local communities, creates goodwill among the residents, potential customers, and contributes to the community's overall success.
- d. Maintain Business Partnership
Developing trustworthy with the business partners and stakeholders that will result in the development of value for the long-term success of the business. Keeping the business afloat through developing new opportunities that may be attained, reducing costs that must be incurred, and also being able to raise awareness for both parties.
- e. Employee Individual Development
Employee individual development planning to align employee and organization objectives, continuously educating and developing its people resources to produce high skilled talents that will add value to the company's existing operations and enable it to expand into the competitive industry.

4.3 Proposed Framework of the Balanced Scorecard

Figure 1. Proposed Strategy Map

As shown in Figure 1, the proposed strategy map features a cause-and-effect relationship between each aim and the ultimate objective, Create Shareholders Value. This strategy map is organized into four perspectives: financial, customer, internal company

process, and learning and growth. There are a total of 17 objectives, including four financial perspective objectives, three customer perspective objectives, seven internal business process objectives, and three learning & growth perspective objectives.

Table 1. Proposed Objective and Measure

BSC Perspective	Objective	Measures
Financial Perspective	Return of Capital	ROI, Return on Capital
	Increase Net Profit	Increase Revenue Growth
	Manage Cost	Division Budget, Budget Allocation
	Increase Profitability	Increase the Business Profitability
Customer Perspective	Build Excellent Service Quality	% Complaint Handled
	Develop Strategic Alliances	Amount of the new customer and business partner
	Increase Brand Awareness	Increase the number of followers per platform, the extent to which a potential customer recognizes and associates the company's business
	Maintain Customer	Target Fulfillment Customer Loyalty Index
Internal Business Process Perspective	Manage Efficient Operation	% Productivity
	Accurate Mine Planning Development	% Mine Plan Accuracy
	Safety Culture	Increase Safety Control Activities
		Number of Work Accidents
	Handle Community	Handle community in the surrounding business unit
	Permits and Licences	Total Achievement of Permits and Licenses
Improve and Provide High Quality Content	Total Positive Content in Media related to PT Gema Kreasi Perdana	
Learning & Growth Perspective	Manage Manpower Planning	Right Sizing Manpower
		Employee Satisfaction
	Develop People	Training per Employee
		Leadership Development
Stable Working Environment	Employee Turnover Rate	

Table 2. HRGA and Strategic Affair Division Scorecard

Perspective	Business	HRGA & Strategic Affair Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	HRGA & Strategic Affair Division Budget	%		Ensure the calculation of employee monthly salaries & benefits is carried out correctly, accurate and on target
		Appropriate budget allocation for each Department	%		Ensure the allocation for each divisions on the HRGA & Strategic Affair Division carried out correctly, accurate and on target
Customer	Increase Brand Awareness	Increase the number of Social Media followers	%	80	Minimum update 2 content per week, showcasing important information about PT Gema Kreasi Perdana
		Online Media Content	content/per week	min 2 - 3	Ensure that media online production content are carried out according to plan
		Social Media Content	content/per week	min 2 - 3	Ensure that media social production content are carried out according to plan
	Manage Efficient Operation	Employee performance	%	100	The realization of performance monitoring activities in the HRGA & Strategic Affair Division
Development of Organizational Structure, Job Desc and SOP		%	100	Ensure the level of completion of system development and organizational structure, job desc and SOP are carried out according to plan	
Internal Business Process	Manage Man Power Planning	Right Sizing Manpower:	%	90	Coordinate the collection of manpower planning data from each Division
		Manpower fulfillment			Supervise and coordinate personnel administration

					Monitor the mapping of workers across all functions on the site
		Improve Recruitment Effectiveness	%	80	Ensure that workers are recruited according to their needs capacities
	Permits and Licenses	Total achievement of permits and certification	%	100	Achieve permits and certification progress for PT GKP
		Government and non-government visits		Zero Complaints	-
Learning & Growth	Develop People	Employee Training:			
		The percentage of training that fits the needs of PT GKP	%	90	Ensure the percentage of training that fits need of the company are carried out according to plan
		Number of training days and programs per year	days		Ensure that training objectives are carried out according to plan
	Create Stable Environment	Employee Turnover	%	10	Evaluate the causes that make employees leave the company
		Employee Satisfaction Rate	%	90	Achieve the average percentage of employee satisfaction
		Complaints Handled	%	90	Coordinate and resolve complaints submitted by employees

Table 3. Manager HR Support and Recruitment Scorecard

Perspective	Business	Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	HRGA & Strategic Affair Division Budget		Zero Complain	Ensure the calculation of employee monthly salaries & benefits is carried out correctly, accurate and on target
		Appropriate budget allocation for HR Support & Recruitment		Zero Complain	Ensure the allocation for each divisions on the HR Support and Recruitment Division

					carried out correctly, accurate and on target
Customer	Build Excellent Service Quality	Retention rate	%	80	Maintain and improve facilities for employees
		Absenteeism	%	< 5	- Conduct training and education - Improve leadership
		Percentage of employee attendance rate	%	99	- Improve welfare - Fair pay and compensation - Comfortable work environment
	Manage Efficient Operation	Employee performances	%	100	Ensure the realization of performance monitoring activities in the HRGA & Strategic Affair Division carried out on target
Development of Organizational Structure, Job Desc and SOP		%	100	- Ensure the level of completion of system development and organizational structure, job desc and SOP are carried out according to plan - Monitor the mapping of workers across all functions on the site (according to the organizational structure).	
Internal Business Process	Manage Man Power Planning	Right Sizing Manpower:			Coordinate the collection of man power planning data from each
		- Manpower fulfillment	%	90	
		Employee Recruitment:			
		- Time needed for Recruitment Process	days	60	Ensure the time needed for Recruitment Process are carried out according to completion plan

	Manage Efficient Operation	Review and Update SOP for HR Support & Recruitment	%	100	Reviewing and looking for gaps in the company's recruitment SOP to be developed and coordination with the Recruitment SOP users related to the SOP content			
		Quarterly audit:						
		- Data fulfillment	%	100% fulfilled	Supervise and coordinate personnel administration (measure all database softcopy dan hardcopy)			
		- Number of audit findings		Zero Violation	Preparation of complete departmental SOP's			
Learning & Growth	Develop People	Employee Training and Development	%	90	Supervising the implementation of the training, Increase training program and employee motivation			
					Ensure that training objectives are carried out according to plan			
					Daftar training soft skill dan hard skill			
	Create Stable Environment	Employee Turnover	%	10	Evaluate the causes that make employees leave, the measures made to satisfy employees and provide them with essential advantages.			
					Employee Satisfaction Rate	%	90	Achieve the average percentage of employee satisfaction
					Complaints Handled	%	90	Coordinate and resolve complaints submitted by employees

Table 4. Superintendent Recruitment Scorecard

Perspective	Business	Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	Recruitment Budget	%		Ensuring the calculation of

					employee monthly salaries & benefits is carried out correctly, accurate and on target
Customer	Increase Brand Awareness	Employer Brand:			
		Maintain and develop the company's Hiring Platform	Week	10 Post per Week	Ensuring that all social media and hiring platforms are updated regularly and look attractive
		Networking with universities and other potential manpower supply institution	Year	5x	Conduct networking activities with universities and institutions with workforce potential
		Conduct Campus Visits	Year	2x	Conducting campus visit activities to promote mining activities and open recruitment
		Management Training	Year	1x	Creating a management training program to recruit the next generation of the company
Internal Business Process	Manage Man Power Planning	Employee Recruitment:			
		Time needed for Recruitment Process	days	60	Ensure the time needed for Recruitment Process are carried out according to completion plan
		Number of recruitments fulfilled	%	100	- Conduct recruitment training - Using the recruitment tools according to the needs of the company
	Manage Efficient Operation	Policy Making:			
	Building/improving Recruitment Standards and SOP	Report	1	Reviewing and looking for gaps in the company's workforce recruitment SOP to be developed	

		Negotiate with users on the SOP	Report	1	Coordination with users for advancements to SOP Recruitment
		Provide Assessment on market talent war	Report	1	Create a talent war map and work strategy in relation to the present talent market battle
		Tools Development:			
		Creating Interview Standards	Document	1	Make standardized interviews (questions, answers and analysis)
		Create Company/Team Jobdesc	Document	1	Establish a jobdesc for all company positions, coordinate with related divisions when creating the job desc
		Create a digital monitoring system	System	Running	Develop a digital platform to track the progress of the recruitment procedure
		Monitoring:			
		Candidate Quality Monitoring	%	90	Number of candidate become permanent
		Performance Review	%	90	Number of candidate become permanent
		Update Jobdesc	Jobdesc	Updated	Update Jobdesc according to the changes
		Team Development:			
		Training Delivery for Recruitment	%	90	- Submit lists of training programs for Recruitment. - Make an evaluation of the training that has been given.
		Create team development training plan	Document	1	Search and create training plans for the recruitment team
Learning & Growth	Develop People				

Table 5. Superintendent Technical Affair Scorecard

Perspective	Business	Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	Expense Budget Proposal preparation (Rencana Anggaran Belanja/RAB)	Yearly	1 Document	Prepare the annual RAB of the Technical Affair Division Ensuring the budget is carried out correctly, accurate and on target.
		RAB realization review	Monthly	1 Document	Carry out a review of the realization of the RAB. Ensuring the realization is carried out correctly, accurate and on target.
Internal Business Process	Permits and Licences	PROJECT: Total achievements related to permits and certification		As instructed	Obtain permits and certification
		Mining databases	Yearly	1 System	Build mining sales and production database
		Budget Work Plan preparation (Rencana Kerja dan Anggaran Belanja/RKAB)	Yearly	1 Reports and Approval Letters	Preparing the new RKAB detailed format in October. Prepare and obtain approval for the RKAB.
		Operations, environmental, safety, and sales factbook	Yearly	1 Book	Compile operation, environmental, safety and sales fact book at the end of Q3
		REPORTS: Regular reports regarding the obligations of Mining License owners (Izin Usaha Pertambangan/IUP)		On time	All routine reports related to the obligations of IUP owners must be submitted
		Non-routine reports related to IUP permits	%	80% on time	Non-routine reports related to IUP permits can be submitted
		Quarterly, monthly & weekly success reports		On time	Submit quarterly, monthly, weekly success reports

		Technical Affair annual plan	Yearly	1 per year	Ensuring the annual plan is structured and socialized
		Submission of main issues related to company activities to Management	%	80	Delivering key issues related to company activities to Management
Learning & Growth	Develop People	Employee training	Yearly	2 documents	Assign below to take at least 2 trainings a year related to mining, English courses, lobby training, etc.
		KRAs and KPIs	Yearly	1 document	All teams must have KRA and KPI every January
		Team performance review	Quarterly	1 document	Carry out quarterly performance reviews at the end of the quarter
		Create team development training plan	Document	1	Search and create training plans for the recruitment team

Table 6. Superintendent Strategic Communication Scorecard

Perspective	Business	Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	Strategic Communication Budget	%	20	Ensuring the Divisional budget is carried out correctly, accurate and on target
Customer	Increase Brand Awareness	Increase the number of followers for Social Media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and Youtube)	followers	10000	Minimum update 2 content per week, showcasing important information about PT Gema Kreasi Perdana
		Media Online Sentiment Gain	%	max 50	Achieve positive sentiment for PT GKP in Online Media by updating positive content about PT Gema Kreasi Perdana
	Improve and Provide High Quality Content	Media Social Sentiment Gain (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and Youtube)	%	max 50	Achieve positive sentiment in Social Media by updating positive content about PT Gema Kreasi Perdana
		Media Online Production	content/per week	min 2	Ensure that media online production content are carried out according to plan

		Media Social Production (Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook)	content/per week	min 2	Ensure that Social Media production content are carried out according to plan
		Average Media Social Reach (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and Youtube)	%	5	Achieve social media Reach
Learning & Growth	Develop People	Employee Training	%	100	Ensure that training objectives are carried out according to plan

Table 7. Superintendent Performance Management and Organizational Development Scorecard

Perspective	Business	Objective	Measurement	Target	Initiatives
Financial	Manage Cost	Performance Management & Organizational Development Budget	%	20	Ensuring the Divisional budget is carried out correctly, accurate and on target
Customer	Build Excellent Service Quality	Improve Service Quality	%	80	Improve employee performance
Internal Business Process	Manage Man Power Planning	Development of Organizational Structure, Job Desc and SOP	%	100	Ensure the level of completion of system development and organizational structure, job desc and SOP are carried out according to plan
Learning & Growth	Develop People	Performance Monitoring	%	100	Ensure the level of realization of performance monitoring activities at the corporate level and division level are carried out according to plan
		Performance Management System Development	%	100	Ensure the completion level of performance management system development are carried out according to plan
		Corporate Culture System Development	%	100	Ensure the completion rate of corporate culture system development are carried out according to plan

		Talent Development System	%	100	Ensure the level of completion of talent development system development are carried out according to plan
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4.4 AHP Calculation

Using the AHP method, weights are assigned to each perspective on the Balanced Scorecard. This was accomplished by distributing questionnaires to expert responders and analyzing the degree of difficulty and importance of each perspective in the Balanced Scorecard for the HRGA and Strategic Affair Division. Taking into account the degree of difficulty in achieving strategic activities and the significance of strategic activities in achieving objectives, each perspective on this Division carries the following weight:

Table 8. AHP Calculation for HRGA and Strategic Affair Division

Perspective	Global Weight	Business	Global Weight	HRGA & Strategic Affair Objective	Global Weight
Financial	13,45%	Manage Cost	13,45%	HRGA & Strategic Affair Division Budget	5,71%
				Appropriate budget allocation for each Department	7,73%
Customer	19,21%	Increase Brand Awareness	7,80%	Increase the number of Social Media followers	1,77%
				Online Media Content	2,75%
				Social Media Content	3,28%
		Manage Efficient Operation	11,41%	Employee performance	4,93%
Development of Organizational Structure, Job Desc and SOP	6,47%				
Internal Business Process	28,33%	Manage Manpower Planning	16,53%	Right Sizing Manpower:	9,63%
				Manpower fulfillment	6,90%
		Permits and Licenses	11,80%	Total achievement of permits and certification	7,62%

				Government and non-government visits	4,18%
Learning & Growth	39,01%	Develop People	19,51%	Employee Training: The percentage of training that fits the needs of PT GKP	14,27%
				Number of training days and programs per year	5,23%
		Create Stable Environment	19,51%	Employee Turnover	5,59%
				Employee Satisfaction Rate	8,90%
				Complaints Handled	5,01%

By looking at the level of difficulty in achieving strategic activities and the degree of importance of strategic activities to achieving objectives, the following is the weight in each perspective on this Division as follows:

- a. Learning & Growth: 39.01%
- b. Internal Business Process: 28.33%
- c. Customers: 19.21%
- d. Finance: 13.45%

The highest weight is on the Learning & Growth perspective because it is related to function from the Department of Human Resources Management as a Business Partner in charge of managing and developing human resources, then the greatest degree of interest lies in that perspective.

5. CONCLUSION

The Balanced Scorecard is a framework for a performance management system intended to bridge the gap between strategy and execution. The objective of the Balanced Scorecard is to convey the company's vision, mission, and strategy so that employees can comprehend the company's direction and objectives, enabling them to achieve them. The suggested new balanced scorecard framework produced sixteen strategic objectives for PT Gema Kreasi Perdana as a result. Then, a cascade mechanism is implemented to ensure that strategic communication from the Corporate Level (tier 1) is effectively communicated to the Division Level (tier 2) and Department Level (tier 3). The cascading process produced a total of 113 strategic objectives and 118 strategic initiatives for HRGA and Strategic Affair Division Managers and Superintendents. With a clear definition of strategic objectives and strategic initiatives at the individual level, it is hoped that employees will be able to comprehend what they must accomplish to align with the company's vision and mission. From the AHP results, the highest weight is on the Learning & Growth perspective because it is related to function from the Department of Human Resources Management as a Business Partner in charge of managing and developing human resources. Therefore, the highest degree of interest lies in that perspective.

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